

Creating the foundations for safe nuclear power in Finland – Thermal hydraulics, safety analyses, safety justification methods research at the LUT University, 2000–2023

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ABSTRACT

The Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology LUT has been the custodian of Finnish nuclear reactor safety research, mainly thermal-hydraulic and regulations-related, from the dawn of the nuclear era in Finland in the mid-1970 s. This paper provides a concise summary of research carried out at LUT University since 2000, presenting work done on large Light-Water Reactors, Small Modular Reactors, gas-cooled reactors, advanced measurement techniques, and nuclear regulations. Independent of the size or shape of the application, one common theme repeats through the decades of effort: a fully representative picture of Nature's behaviour can only be obtained by a balanced combination of experiments, scaling analyses and analytical modelling. Performance shortcomings have been forestalled and resolution of emerging safety issues supported by experiments at LUT University.

1. Introduction

Finland decided to embark on nuclear construction in the early 1970 s. The first two nuclear reactors to be built in the Loviisa power plant were bought from the Soviet Union, but the Finnish owner required them to be built to Western safety standards of the day, necessitating numerous adaptations and new design features, including emergency core cooling systems and a leak-tight containment structure. The Soviet safety philosophy was different, and therefore the reactor supplier was not able to provide all information required for the safety demonstration, in some cases because the Supplier itself did not possess the information. Therefore, the Finnish owner and the Finnish regulator deemed it necessary to launch an experimental program to study safety-relevant phenomena first-hand.

The very first experiments focused on Large Break Loss-of-Coolant Accidents, which were the fashion of the day in the late 1970 s, and where reflooding of an overheated core from both the bottom and the top was of interest due to the ECCS configuration of the Loviisa reactors. Such tests were feasible in electrically heated test bundles, first in a transparent test section, and then in a U-tube vessel model. In the early

1980 s, the significance of Small Break LOCAs was recognized, and test facilities grew much more complex, to model the whole primary system with steam generators, first as one loop and eventually as a three-loop representation of the six-loop Loviisa VVER as PACTEL facility in 1990. VVER reactors feature horizontal steam generators and, in the six-loop versions, loop seals in the hot legs – therefore many unique behaviours that differ from Western designs.

During the 1990 s, passive safety systems started to emerge, and testing of many passive systems and components was carried out, including gravity-driven Core Make-up Tank configurations proposed at the time for the Westinghouse AP600. Passive components such as steam-driven hydroaccumulators were tested in full-scale conditions as well for the Siemens SWR-1000 BWR concept. These tests showed in systems where saturated steam encounters deeply subcooled coolant the performance can suffer greatly from direct contact condensation. Severe accident management systems such as the first bottom-cooled core catchers were also tested at the time.

In the 2000 s, boiling water reactor suppression pool containment phenomena started to receive more attention. Direct contact condensation (DCC) had already been observed in passive system tests and was studied much more in pressure suppression pool (PSP) geometry where

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Nomenclature*Abbreviations*

12UPS	Non-Class 1E 12-hour Uninterruptible Power Supply System	IB	Intermediate Break
AES-2006	Russian 1200 MWe VVER (PWR) nuclear power plant design	ICIS	In-Core Instrumentation System
AOO	Anticipated Operational Occurrences	IE	Infrequent Event
AP600	Advanced Passive 600 MWe PWR design by Westinghouse	iPWR	Integral Pressurized Water Reactor
ATWS	Anticipated Transients Without Scram	IRWST	In-containment Refueling Water Storage Tank
AXE	Axial Wire-Mesh Sensor	KTH	Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan, Royal Institute of Technology
BDBE	Beyond Design Basis Event	LHSI	Low Head Safety Injection
BOL	Beginning-Of-Life	LOCA	Loss-Of-Coolant Accident
BWR	Boiling Water Reactor	LOOP	Loss Of Offsite Power
CBVS	Containment Building Ventilation System	LTC	Long-Term Cooling
CCWS	Component Cooling Water System	LUT	Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology
CDF	Core Damage Frequency	LWR	Light Water Reactor
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics	MCP	Main Coolant Pump
CFDS	Containment Flooding and Drain System	MCR	Main Control Room
CGCS	Combustible Gas Control System	McSAFER	Improving Safety Analysis Methodologies and Moving from Traditional to High-fidelity Safety Analysis Tools for Small Modular Reactors
CHRS	Control Room Habitability System	MFWS	Main Feedwater System
CIS	Containment Isolation System	MHSI	Medium Head Safety Injection
CIV	Containment Isolation Valves	MMR	Micro-Modular Reactor, helium-cooled graphite moderated microreactor developed by Ultra Safe Nuclear Corporation Ltd.
CMSS	Core Melt Stabilization System	MOTEL	MOdular TESt Loop
CRACS	Main Control Room Air Conditioning System	MSIV	Main Steam Isolation Valve
CRDS	Control Rod Drive System	MSLB	Main Steam Line Break
CRE	Control Room Envelope	MSRT	Main Steam Relief Train
CRVS	Control Room Ventilation System	MSSS	Main Steam Supply System
CVCS	Chemical and Volume Control System	MSSV	Main Steam System Valve
CWS	Circulating Water System	MTC	Moderator Temperature Coefficient
DBA	Design Basis Accident	“N/A”	Not Applicable
DBE	Design Basis Event	NEA	Nuclear Energy Agency
DCC	Direct Contact Condensation	NETNUC	New Type Nuclear Reactors, Finnish national research project on Gen IV technologies funded by the Academy of Finland and Fortum between 2008 and 2011.
DEC	Design Extension Condition	NO	Normal Operation
DEM	Discrete Element Method	NPSS	Normal Power Supply System
DHRS	Decay Heat Removal System	OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
DiD	Defence-in-Depth	ORSAC	Overall safety conceptual framework
DN20	Nominal (internal) diameter 20 mm	OSAFE	Development of Framework for justification of Overall Safety
EBS	Extra Borating System	PACS	Priority Actuation and Control System
ECCS	Emergency Core Cooling System	PACTEL	Parallel Channel TESt Loop at LUT University, Finland.
EDG	Emergency Diesel Generator	PANDA	Passive Nachwärmeabfuhr- und Druckabbau-Testanlage (Passive Decay Heat Removal and Depressurization Test Facility) at PSI, Switzerland
EFWS	Emergency Feedwater System	PAS	Process Automation System
EHS	Effective Heat Source	PASI	Passive Heat Removal Test Facility
EMS	Effective Momentum Source	PASTELS	Passive Systems: Simulating thermal hydraulics with experimental studies
EPGBVS	Emergency Power Generating Building Ventilation System	PBMR	Pebble Bed Modular Reactor
EPR	Evolutionary Pressurized Reactor	PDS	Primary Depressurization System
EPSS	Class 1E Emergency Power Supply System	PDSV	Primary Depressurization System Valves
ESF	Engineered Safety Feature	PIV	Particle Image Velocimetry
ESWPBVS	Essential Service Water Pump Building Ventilation System	PKL	Primärkreislauf-Versuchsanlage (Primary Coolant Loop Test Facility)
ESWS	Essential Service Water System	POOLEX	Condensation Pool Test Facility
ETHARINUS	Experimental Thermal Hydraulics for Analysis, Research and Innovations in Nuclear Safety	PPOOLEX	Pressurized Condensation Pool Test Facility
EUPS	Class 1E Uninterruptible Power Supply System	PPS	Preferred Power System
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform	PR	Pattern Recognition
FONESYS:	The FORum & NETwork of SYStem Thermal-Hydraulic Codes in Nuclear Reactor Thermal-Hydraulics	PRA	Probabilistic Risk Assessment
FWIV	Feedwater Isolation Valve	PRT	Pressurizer Relief Tank
Gd ₂ O ₃	Gadolinia	PS	Protection System
GOTHIC	Containment Thermal-Hydraulic Code	PSI	Paul Scherrer Institut
HPR1000	Chinese 1000 MWe range PWR		
HTR-PM	High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor - Pebble Bed Module		
I&C	Instrumentation and Control		
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency		

PSP	Pressure Suppression Pool (BWR)	SCWS	Site Cooling Water System
PSCIV	Primary System Containment Isolation Valve	SEF-POOL	Separate Effect Facility
PSRV	Pressurizer Safety Relief Valves	SFP	Spent Fuel Pool
PTS	Pressurized Thermal Shock	SG	Steam Generator
PWR	Pressurized Water Reactor	SGTR	Steam Generator Tube Rupture
RBVS	Reactor Building Ventilation System	SICS	Safety Information and Control System
RCB	Reactor Containment Building	SILENCE	(Significant Light and Heavy Water Reactor Thermal Hydraulic Experiments Network for the Consistent Exploitation of the Data)
RCCA	Rod Cluster Control Assembly	SIS	Safety Injection System
RCCWS	Reactor Component Cooling Water System	SIS/RHR	Safety Injection System/Residual Heat Removal
RCPB	Reactor Coolant Pressure Boundary	SMR	Small Modular Reactor
RCS	Reactor Coolant System	SRS	Safety Report Series
RCSL	Reactor Control, Surveillance and Limitation	SWR1000	Siedewasserreaktor 1000, Siemens 1250 MWe BWR with passive safety features. Later known as Kerena™.
RHRS	Residual Heat Removal System	SSCIV	Secondary System Containment Isolation Valve
RPV	Reactor Pressure Vessel	STUK	Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority in Finland
RRV	Reactor Recirculation Valve	TG	Turbine Generator
RSB	Reactor Shield Building	TG I&C	Turbine Generator Instrumentation and Control
SAFIR	Safety of Nuclear Power Plants – Finnish National Research Programme (2010, 2014, 2018, 2022)	TRISO	Tri-structural Isotropic
SAHRS	Severe Accident Heat Removal System	UHS	Ultimate Heat Sink
SA I&C	Severe Accident Instrumentation and Control	UO ₂	Uranium dioxide
SAM	Severe Accident Management	U.S. EPR	United States Evolutionary Pressurized Reactor
SAS	Safety Automation System	U.S. NRC	United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission
SB	Small Break	VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland
SBO	Station Blackout	VVER	Voda-Vodanyi Energeticheskii Reaktor, Soviet/Russian PWR.
SBODG	Station Blackout Diesel Generator	WMS	Wire-Mesh Sensor
SBORVS	Station Blackout Room Ventilation System	YVL	Regulatory Guides on Nuclear Safety
SBVS	Safeguard Building Controlled-Area Ventilation System		
SBVSE	Electrical Division of Safeguard Building Ventilation System		

chugging testing could be carried out, first in atmospheric pressure on the POOLEX facility and later with pressurized model PPOOLEX. After an EPR was ordered in 2003, the system thermal-hydraulics test facility PACTEL was modified by replacing three horizontal steam generators with two vertical U-tubes steam generators.

The first decades of LUT thermal-hydraulic research have been summarized in (Purhonen, 2007). The thermal-hydraulic experimentation has been supported by system code analyses from late 1980 s.

Analytical capabilities have been developed for CFD modelling of both turbulent and two-phase flows (Tanskanen, 2012; Patel, 2017) and coupled thermal hydraulics / reactor physics calculations (Suikkanen, 2014; Rintala, 2022).

During the 2010 s, more work proved necessary on gravity-driven containment heat removal loops. Earlier testing on natural circulation in primary systems of the VVERs and U-tube PWRs had already provided a good picture of how gravity-driven flows behave in higher system pressures; containment coolers often operate pressures below the containment design pressure, which is comparatively low, around 0.5 MPa(a). Integral PWR designs with new steam generator geometries started to emerge, and therefore a NuScale-like test facility MOTEL was constructed, with electrical heaters and a helical coil steam generator model. (For a description of NuScale design, see e.g. (U.S.NRC, 2023).) In addition to system testing, separate effects tests were designed and carried out for a variety of applications, such as details of reactor vessel wall heat transfer or exotic material behaviours under accident conditions (thermal insulation, vibration damping materials).

In the following five sections, highlights of the nuclear reactor related research at LUT are provided. Chapter 2 covers work done for large LWRs, Chapter 3 focuses on SMRs, Chapter 4 on Gas-cooled reactors and Chapter 5 on advanced measurement techniques used. Chapter 6 provides an outlook on future developments and Chapter 7 concludes the paper.

2. Large reactor related studies

This section presents selected experimental campaigns that yielded results considered groundbreaking in one way or another. Section 2.1 discusses the design of a bitumen-coolant separator trap developed for Olkiluoto 3. Section 2.2 covers passive containment cooler testing, section 2.3 PWR system thermal hydraulics, Section 2.4 BWR containment thermal-hydraulics, and Section 2.5 separate effects tests for Pressurised Thermal Shock.

2.1. Enabling bitumen for vibration damping in the containment

The first commissioning tests at full operating parameters at Olkiluoto 3 EPR revealed significant structural vibrations in the pressurizer surge line. The plant Supplier chose viscous dampers to dampen the vibrations. These dampers were to be installed in the containment close to the surge line.

The selected viscous dampers contain several hundred kilograms of viscous mass, a mixture of commercial-grade bitumen materials. Bitumen is immiscible with water; unfortunately, over the temperature range of post-accident conditions of Olkiluoto 3, the density of bitumen is identical to water density to within 0.5 %. The integrity of the dampers cannot be guaranteed in case of a pipe break in their vicinity. A risk of released bitumen block coolant recirculation in post-accident conditions was recognised. Bitumen can collect on filters by itself or by interaction with thermal insulation debris. There is no information in the open literature about bitumen behaviour in reactor accident conditions inside the containment.

LUT Nuclear Engineering laboratory carried out experiments into bitumen behaviour and developed a trap that separates the bitumen, fibrous thermal insulation debris from pressuriser, and reactor coolant from each other fully passively, without moving parts or operator actions. The trap is installed in the flow path from the pressuriser compartment to the containment sumps. The performance of the trap

Fig. 1. A mixture of coolant, fibrous debris and bitumen falls into the trap from the upper floor. The bulk of the bitumen floats against the blind screen (1a); red arrows show coolant travelling through the perforated floor (2), collecting fibrous debris there. Blind screen (1b) provides an overflow route in case head loss over the floor (2) becomes excessive, guaranteeing limited water holdup in the trap. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

was independently verified by large-scale experiments in the Areva laboratory at Erlangen, Germany.

LUT testing covered all accident phases that bitumen could be exposed to, namely debris generation by high-pressure steam jet, transport with hot water coolant, filtering through steel meshes, and interaction with fibrous debris beds. Each phenomenon was studied separately.

The following key observations were made (Hyvärinen et al., 2019):

- 1) Under saturated steam jets from a 5 MPa vessel through a DN20 nozzle, all bitumen samples eroded slightly at the point of impact, releasing very small (<1 mm) droplets due to jet shear. The bulk of the bitumen heats up and creeps out of the jet zone of influence. Therefore, a relatively slow release of the bulk of the bitumen into coolant emanating from a LOCA can be expected; release is mainly due to gradual heat-up of the mass instead of rapid dispersion under LOCA jets
- 2) Flume testing of hot bitumen (initially up to 140 °C) in coolant heated up to 95 °C shows that bitumen readily follows the flow, being of low viscosity at this high temperature. Upon contact with filter mesh, bitumen accumulates on the meshes, beginning to seep through slowly. Therefore, “normal” mesh filters can delay the passage and even get partially clogged by bitumen spreading over the mesh.
- 3) Bitumen flotation can be induced if water falls to the flume, simulating water falling from a higher to a lower floor. Falling water entrains air into the water body, and air bubbles attach to bitumen chunks. Flotation can be used to separate bitumen and fibres from each other.
- 4) Fibrous debris bed traps bitumen efficiently, forming impermeable patches.

A schematic of the bitumen trap is shown in Fig. 1.

In conclusion, bitumen can be safely used as vibration damping material inside a nuclear reactor containment. LUT Nuclear Engineering designed trap can separate coolant, fibrous debris and bitumen from each other simply by virtue of gravity, air entrainment, and appropriate geometry. The floor area (item 2 in Fig. 1) must be large enough to be able to collect the fibrous debris with acceptably low head loss.

2.2. Robustness of passive heat removal by containment wall condenser

Naturally circulating heat removal loops are designed as passive safety systems in many light water reactors for containment cooling. Such loops operate passively, relying on relatively small gravitational pressure differences only. Open passive containment cooling systems are included e.g. in the Russian AES-2006 (VVER-1200) type (Bakhmet'ev et al., 2009), the Chinese HPR1000 type (Xing et al., 2016), and the Korean iPower type (Lee et al., 2017) nuclear power plant designs.

Open passive containment cooling loops often operate at low atmospheric pressure and are sensitive to boiling oscillations due to a large water-steam density difference. Experiments in prototypical conditions are needed to verify the performance of passive safety systems under postulated accident scenarios. PASI, an open passive containment cooling system test facility, was designed and constructed at LUT University, Lappeenranta, Finland. The reference for the one-loop PASI test facility is the passive containment heat removal system of the AES-2006 type pressurized water reactor. The design height scale of the PASI facility versus the reference system is 1:2 (Fig. 2). The PASI facility consists of a pressure vessel simulating containment conditions and a circulation loop comprising an in-containment heat exchanger, riser and downcomer pipelines, a sparger, and a water pool as a heat sink / water reservoir. (Kouhia et al., 2021).

The first characterizing experiments of the facility included natural circulation experiments in addition to pressure and heat loss experiments (Riikonen et al., 2022). The PASI experiments have been done in the Finnish national nuclear safety research programme SAFIR2022 (Riikonen et al., 2023a) and have continued within the EU PASTELS (Passive Systems: Simulating thermal hydraulics with experimental studies) project, with funding from the EU Horizon 2020 program (Montout et al., 2022, 2023). The PASI experiments within the EU PASTELS project quantify the sensitivity of the heat removal capability to the loop flow resistance, pool water level, containment heat load, and map more thoroughly the loop heat removal capability, including operating conditions where instabilities or flow oscillations appear.

The loop flow resistance experiments with the PASI facility were performed to quantify the sensitivity of the heat removal capability of the system versus the loop flow resistance, and to map the loop operating conditions where instabilities or flow oscillations appear. Altogether four experiments were conducted varying the heating power and the loop mass flow resistance (Telkkä et al., 2023a). During each experiment, the loop flow resistance was varied by a throttling valve in the downcomer pipeline, keeping the selected heating powers to the containment vessel constant (Fig. 3). The dimensionless pressure loss coefficient for each valve position was calculated from the data of the valve pressure loss testing, which was performed before the actual flow resistance experiments. The valve local loss coefficient was varied by a factor of 1 to almost 1000.

It was observed that the system removed heat efficiently over three decades of loop flow resistances. The loop mass flow rate was stable until the temperatures in the riser approached saturation conditions. Then geysering-like flow oscillations (Hou et al., 2016, 2017; Yan et al., 2017) occurred in the riser. The heat removal capability of the loop remained consistently effective despite the appearing flow oscillations. However, inside the tube bank, flow can be nonuniform, and irregular internal circulatory cycling between parallel heat exchanger tubes can be observed.

The results of the experiment also showed that there is a loose

Fig. 2. General view of the PASI test facility.

Fig. 3. Downcomer mass flow rate (error margin ± 0.15 kg/s) in three experiments with different heating powers. Downcomer valve position: 1 – fully open (dimensionless pressure loss coefficient $\xi = 122 (\xi_0)$), 2 – 50 % closed ($\xi/\xi_0 = 1.19$), 3 – 81 % closed ($\xi/\xi_0 = 7.46$), 4 – 86 % closed ($\xi/\xi_0 = 14.1$), 5 – 91 % closed ($\xi/\xi_0 = 275$), 6 – 95 % closed ($\xi/\xi_0 = 941$).

connection between the heating power and the oscillation frequency of the loop flow and the oscillation amplitude. Increased heating power increases the oscillation frequency and amplitude only slightly.

Increasing the loop flow resistance decreases the amplitude. After each increase in the flow resistance, void fraction in the riser increased and the system quickly found at once a new quasi-steady state where heat

Fig. 4. PWR PACTEL facility.

was adequately transferred. At high resistances, flow around the loop practically stops, but adequate heat removal continues as long as counter-current flow in the riser provides adequate supply of water to the heat exchanger.

The system can remove heat effectively from the containment vessel even when the water pool is empty of water as long as there is still water in the loop. The amplitude of the flow oscillations decreased with the low water levels.

There is a pressure balancing hole in the sparger structure. The system behaviour changed when the pool water level dropped below the sparger pressure balancing hole elevation, as the frequency of the oscillations increased. When the pool water level was above the hole, a relatively small and constant natural circulation flow between the flow oscillation peaks occurred in the loop. As the water level decreased below the hole, the water circulation around the loop became impossible. Instead, water oscillated between the downcomer and riser sides of the loop.

The system can remove heat effectively from the containment vessel during the refilling of the water pool with cold water, too. The experiment results showed that the system behaviour changed when the pool

water level increased above the sparger pressure balancing hole elevation. When the pool water level was below the hole, the water could not flow through the loop. The flow in the loop was oscillating until the water level in the riser reached the hole and enabled the single-phase natural circulation through the loop.

The effect of the pressure balancing hole on the system behaviour was also studied by blocking the hole. The test results showed that the system behaviour did not change significantly. The system still transferred heat efficiently evaporating water in the heat exchanger.

The results of the PASI experiments indicate that a passive open loop heat removal system can efficiently remove heat from the containment and maintain the containment pressure on a safe level even at very high loop flow resistances, up to almost 1000 larger than nominal. Loop flow oscillations do not hamper heat removal. The low water pool level or blocking the sparger pressure balancing hole does not disturb the system either. Hence, it can be concluded that this kind of passive heat removal system seems not to be sensitive to changes in the loop friction or the water pool level. The system is capable of self-adjusting to changing operating boundary conditions.

Fig. 5. Anticipated behaviour of the reactor cooling system during a LOCA when nitrogen in the accumulator is released to the primary side.

2.3. Integral PWR system experiments, highlighting adverse effects of non-condensable gases on core cooling and computer code performance

The PWR PACTEL integral facility (Rantakaulio et al., 2010; Kouhia et al., 2012, 2013) was designed and constructed at LUT University to gain experience on the behaviour of an EPR type PWRs and to study unique EPR accident management procedures. The facility consists of a U-shaped reactor pressure vessel model, two loops with vertical steam generators, a pressurizer, and emergency core cooling systems including nitrogen-driven accumulators (Fig. 4). The core can be powered by a maximum of 1 MW electric power supply. The maximum core power corresponds roughly to the scaled residual heating power of the EPR reactor. The total height of the PWR PACTEL pressure vessel model corresponds to the pressure vessel height of an EPR. The volume ratio between the pressure vessels in PWR PACTEL and an EPR is about 1/405. The pressurizer is shorter than in an EPR. The volume ratio between the pressurizers of PWR PACTEL and EPR is 1/562.

Since the commissioning of the facility in 2009, until today over 60 experiments have been performed with the facility. The research is focused on studying phenomena related to the operation with vertical steam generators. The experiment topics covered so far are pressure and heat losses, natural circulation, small break LOCA, loss of feedwater, flow reversal in steam generator (Kauppinen et al., 2015a), loop seal behaviour (Kauppinen et al., 2015b), station blackout, release of non-condensable gases (Riikonen et al., 2018), pump trip, and several power plant transients. The experimental work with PWR PACTEL has been carried out in projects within the national nuclear safety research programmes SAFIR2014, SAFIR2018 and SAFIR2022 (Riikonen et al., 2015, 2019, 2023b) and in the OECD/NEA's joint projects (OECD/NEA, 2023).

LUT University participated in the OECD/NEA PKL Phase 3 (2012–2016) and the OECD/NEA PKL Phase 4 (2016–2020) projects and participates in the ongoing OECD/NEA ETHARINUS (2020–2024) project (OECD/NEA, 2023). The experiments performed in the OECD/

NEA projects are highly relevant to the improvement and validation of thermal hydraulics safety codes, as well as to maintain competence and expertise in this field which is an important goal for the NEA member countries. In the OECD/NEA PKL Phase 3 project, safety issues related to beyond design basis accident transients with significant core heat-up and events in the cold shut down state were covered. The PKL, ROCOM, PMK and PWR PACTEL facilities were used in the test program. LUT University complemented the project with integral tests with PWR PACTEL on the cool down process in the presence of isolated steam generators, station blackout, and flow reversal in steam generator heat exchange tubes.

The experiments in the OECD/NEA PKL Phase 4 project focused on safety issues relevant for the current PWR plants as well as for new PWR design concepts by means of systematic parameter studies on thermal hydraulic phenomena and transient tests under postulated accident scenarios. LUT University provided to the project three PWR PACTEL integral tests complementing the PKL experiments on IB/SB-LOCA. The effect of the connection line between the upper plenum and downcomer on the piston effect at the presence of nitrogen in the primary side (Fig. 5) was studied (Riikonen et al., 2015, 2019).

The objectives of the OECD/NEA ETHARINUS project are to investigate phenomena where the knowledge base for safety assessment is not sufficiently developed and to provide qualified data for thermal hydraulics code development and validation for the analysis of the key safety issues. Focus of the investigations is on studies related to loss of coolant accident addressing design extension conditions for small break LOCA scenarios and two-phase flow thermal hydraulic phenomena for intermediate break LOCA scenarios, on studies related to core cooling performance under a partial core blockage, on studies related to the effectiveness of passive heat removal systems, and on studies related to cool-down procedures after a multiple steam generator tube rupture scenario (OECD/NEA, 2023). LUT University participates in the project with two PWR PACTEL integral tests studying the effect of a common-cause failure of the cold leg safety injection system check valves and

Fig. 6. Pressures in the primary and secondary sides in the experiments to study the effect of available volume (left) and nitrogen mass (right).

the planned actions when the cold leg safety injection is not possible (Riikonen et al., 2023b).

With the PWR PACTEL facility, one long-term research activity has been in studying the effect of nitrogen release from an accumulator into the primary system during a LOCA conditions. For example, the PWR PACTEL nitrogen experiments with a hot leg break (Riikonen et al.,

2018) showed that the accumulator nitrogen could stop the primary side depressurization and cause a core heat-up at a reactor pressure above or close to a typical low-pressure safety injection shut-off head. This separation of primary and secondary pressures was not captured by thermal-hydraulic system codes, but codes predicted that primary pressure would follow the secondary to well within the range of low-pressure

Fig. 7. PPOOLEX (a) and SEF-POOL (b) facilities of LUT University. Bubble boundaries detected with the pattern-recognition algorithm in PPOOLEX test (c) and improved edge detection by the border repair method in SEF-POOL test (d).

Fig. 8. Comparison of pool temperatures between measured data (a) and EHS-EMS simulation (b) during thermal stratification, mixing and re-stratification phases of a PPOOLEX experiment.

safety injection. Had the code calculations represented an actual plant, the plant response to the accident would have been dangerously misrepresented. It was therefore important to have more testing to map the range of the pressures at which the observed decoupling of the primary and secondary side pressures appears as a function of the break size, released nitrogen mass, and primary side volume available for nitrogen. The experiment results on the subject provide important reference database for the code validation purposes, as thermal-hydraulic system codes have difficulties catching the phenomenon (Kauppinen et al., 2019).

In the test to investigate the volume available for nitrogen, only one loop of the facility was used. The transient with either one or two loops and the steam generators connected to the system had a similar effect on the occurrence of the decoupling of the pressures, the pressure value levels at the decoupling, and the length of the decoupling period (Fig. 6 left) (Riikonen et al., 2023b). The effect of the released nitrogen mass was studied in the experiment with the reduced amount of nitrogen. The amount of injected nitrogen affects the decoupling of the pressures (Fig. 6 right). With the reduced amount of nitrogen, the decoupling began when the nitrogen reached the break. After that, the primary side pressure decreased slowly but did not follow the secondary side pressure, as in the reference experiment. Nitrogen continued to cause a core heat-up at a reactor pressure close to a typical low-pressure safety injection shut-off head.

In the reference experiment, the nitrogen release was larger, and the decoupling of the primary and secondary side pressures began already when the nitrogen release to the primary side began. That caused a core heat-up at the higher reactor pressure. Some of the nitrogen flowed out through the break but the experiment results also indicated the presence of nitrogen in the steam generator heat exchange tubes. The effect of the break size on the nitrogen release and the decoupling of the pressures is planned to be studied in 2024 or 2025. Test data can be used in the development and validation of computer codes for the safety analyses of nuclear power plants.

2.4. BWR suppression pool: Chugging and direct contact condensation

The BWR cooling system is more compact than the PWR because of the absence of a secondary circuit. The small containment volume of BWRs could bring on the possibility that a large amount of steam must be rapidly condensed into a Pressure Suppression Pool (PSP) during LOCA via direct contact condensation (DCC). The flow phenomena in the PSP during steam blowdown, either through vent pipes or spargers, are inherently three-dimensional and involve a two-phase and/or multiphase flow with rapid heat and mass transfer, irregular violent pressure oscillations, thermal stratification, and pool mixing. Injected

steam causes structural loads to the PSP and demands a lot of its strength. Since 2002, extensive experimental studies concerning PSP phenomena have been carried out at LUT University as part of several national and international projects, both with the open pool test facility (POOLEX) and the pressurizing drywell-wetwell suppression pool facility (PPOOLEX). The PPOOLEX test facility is a scaled-down model of Nordic-type BWR containment (Fig. 7(a)). The 31 m³ stainless steel pressurized vessel has a total height of 7.45 m and a diameter of 2.4 m. It consists of dry well and wet well compartments separated by an intermediate floor. A route for air/steam flow from the dry well to the wet well is created by a vertical blowdown pipe attached asymmetrically underneath the floor. The test data of steam blowdown experiments have been utilized for studying essential phenomena which govern the pool behaviour and for computational models' validation purposes.

A small-scale facility called Separate Effect Facility - Pool (SEF-POOL) has been constructed in collaboration with KTH and the Technical Research Centre of Finland (VTT). The facility is designed to measure the effective momentum produced by steam injection through a sparger and to conduct a detailed study of DCC phenomena in horizontal steam injection cases of spargers. The SEF-POOL facility is a rectangular, uninsulated, stainless-steel box with viewing windows on the side walls. It is open on top, 1.5 m long, 0.3 m wide, and 0.6 m high (Fig. 6(b)). The direct local measurements of PSP phenomena are challenging because of rapid pressure oscillation, micro length, and turbulent two-phase flow time scales. Nevertheless, if visual observation of the PSP interior is possible, modern measurement techniques like high-speed cameras, particle image velocimetry (PIV), and wire-mesh sensors (WMSs) can extract meaningful data. To this end, novel measurement methods and high-speed cameras are being used to record the experiments of PPOOLEX and SEF-POOL in a detailed manner at LUT.

Using the high-frequency measurement data and high-speed video recordings of the DCC tests, a pattern recognition (PR) based image analysis algorithm was developed for both vertical and horizontal steam injection cases for the evaluation of bubble diameter, surface area, volume, velocity, acceleration, and frequencies of the condensing steam bubbles (Hujala et al., 2018a; Patel et al., 2017, 2023). In addition, Fast Fourier transform (FFT) was used for frequency analysis of the pattern-recognized data (Hujala et al., 2018b). The recognized bubble boundaries and improved edge detection in the border repair method of the algorithm can recognize and track successfully chugging and bubbling condensation oscillation modes of rapidly condensing steam bubbles throughout their entire life span (Fig. 7 (c) and (d)). The work on the PR algorithm and related sophisticated measurement techniques are discussed in more detail in Section 5.

A complex interplay between steam venting into a PSP and condensation leads either to thermal stratification or mixing of the pool.

Fig. 9. (a) PTS test rig and (b) typical heat transfer coefficients from the test.

Experiments show that strong thermal stratification can develop in the pool during prototypic steam injection conditions. This means that the pool mass below the stratification boundary fails to participate in heat absorption, reducing the size of the actual heat sink.

Prediction of this kind of long-term thermal behaviour of a large water pool with CFD codes is time consuming and requires lots of computational capacity because the associated DCC phenomenon needs to be solved. Effective Heat Source (EHS) and Effective Momentum Source (EMS) models have been proposed by Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan (KTH) to predict the development of thermal stratification and mixing during a steam injection into a large pool of water (Li et al., 2014a). The simplified EHS and EMS models would reduce the needed computational capacity. The premise of these models is that due to the difference in spatial and time scales between the DCC phenomena and large pool behaviour, only the integral effects of DCC on the pool should be modelled. These effects are defined as heat and momentum sources, which determine the large-scale pool circulation and temperature distribution. The EHS and EMS models for steam injection through blow-down pipes have been successfully validated with the help of the LUT's PPOOLEX stratification and mixing experiments and implemented to the containment thermal-hydraulic code GOTHIC by KTH (Li et al., 2014b). The numerical simulations with GOTHIC quantitatively capture the complex transient pool behaviour and are in excellent agreement with the transient averaged pool temperature and water level in the pool (Fig. 8) (Li et al., 2018; Gallego-Marcos et al., 2018a).

The concepts of the EHS and EMS models have been further extended to spargers and validated against the PPOOLEX and SEF-POOL tests at LUT and PANDA tests at Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI) in Switzerland (Gallego-Marcos, 2018; Gallego-Marcos et al., 2018b, 2019a, 2019b). The validated models have been applied to the full-scale analysis of a Nordic BWR pressure suppression pool during a steam injection through spargers (Gallego-Marcos et al., 2019c). The analysis results suggest that further development of the EHS/EMS correlations and computational models is justified to enable modelling of regimes and conditions, which have not yet been studied in experiments but would be critically important and can completely change the PSP stratification and mixing behaviour.

The development of thermal stratification in a PSP is of safety concern since it reduces the steam condensation capacity of the pool, increases the pool surface temperature, and thus leads to higher containment pressures compared with thoroughly mixed pool conditions. It has been suggested that mixing induced by spray had a role in the drop of pressure in Fukushima Unit 3, where pressure build-up in the containment during the first 20 h after station blackout was attributed to

stratification in the pool (Jo et al., 2016). Addressing stratification and mixing issues in a large water pool is thus essential. Additional data on pool behaviour are needed to validate computer models and evaluate safety margins. PPOOLEX, PPOOLEX and SEF-POOL tests at LUT have contributed by increasing knowledge of small-scale phenomena affecting the adequate heat and momentum sources during steam injection into the PSP via vent pipes and spargers.

2.5. Lifetime extension of PWRs – Addressing pressurised thermal shock

Pressurised thermal shock (PTS) is an overcooling transient which induces thermal loads on the reactor pressure vessel (RPV) under pressurized conditions. These thermal loads may cause large stresses and instability of possible flaws present inside the RPV wall. Therefore, assessment of mixing behaviour is important to predict the thermal loads. At LUT University, experiments were conducted aiming to analyse the effects of the inadvertent cooling and PTS related to the pressure vessel for Loviisa NPP (VVER-440 reactors). A mock-up test facility was designed which represented a sector of the RPV wall (Fig. 9(a)). The test section considered a rectangular shape by ignoring the curvature of the RPV due to the radius of the wall being significantly greater than the thickness of the wall in the RPV. The main component in the setup was a rectangular steel bar (100 mm x 150 mm x 1700 mm) which had heaters on one side and was enclosed in a flow channel (100 mm x 300 mm cross-section) on the opposite side. The thickness of the bar was the same as the wall thickness of the pressure vessel. Heat transfer from the pressure vessel wall to the water was studied experimentally to determine the heat transfer coefficients for further calculations (Merisaari et al., 2011). Results revealed that the applied correlations were unable to predict the initial few minutes of the cooling transient (Fig. 9(b)). In particular, the initial heat transfer is much higher than the correlations suggest. (This is understandable because most correlations have been derived from measurements at constant conditions.)

In the subsequent phase of the cooling transient, natural convection correlation gave the most accurate approximation while the forced convection correlations failed to yield the heat transfer coefficient.

Later this PTS test facility was modified and utilized for further tests for contract work for other customers to evaluate the heat transfer characteristics at the RPV wall related to PTS in cold leg ECC injection. A test series was carried out at LUT University with different inlet flow rates and varying water inlet temperatures. Particle image velocimetry (PIV) was used successfully to measure the flow profile in the flow channel. Chapter 5.3 includes further details on PIV results.

During these tests, a skewed vertical velocity distribution in the

Fig. 10. Modules comprising the pressure vessel (left) and insight on the SMR design (right) of the MOTEL facility.

rectangular channel could be induced by minimal axial offset (of about 1 mm) of the inlet piping. Such geometry sensitivity is to be expected due to the opening angle of the fitting between the round pipe and rectangular channel; this skewness will not be reproduced in CFD calculations, if the channel geometry is modelled as ideal (symmetric), but can be reproduced if the geometric offset is modelled in the mesh.

3. Small Modular Reactors: New component geometries, siting near population

Several so-called Small Modular Reactor concepts have emerged during the last decades, and many of them have novel thermal-hydraulic design solutions that merit exploratory and verification testing. Section 3.1 describes MOTEL, an electrically heated integral PWR test facility. SMRs also challenge present notions of safety assessment and licensing, and Finnish authorities have contracted LUT University to provide technical support for SMR-related legislation updates. This is described in Section 3.2. Finally, Section 3.3 presents a reactor

dedicated to district heating.

3.1. MOTEL experiments

MOTEL (MODular TEST Loop) is an integral test facility recently commissioned in the LUT nuclear safety research laboratory. Modularity has been the guiding design philosophy behind MOTEL, as the facility consists of exchangeable main components that could be replaced with functionally similar ones but with different designs. This way, the facility could be configured to represent various reactor designs. The current implementation of MOTEL represents a prototypical integral pressurized water small modular reactor (SMR) operating with natural circulation. The facility enables experimental research of various features related to SMRs.

MOTEL was commissioned in 2020, and the characterizing tests were run in 2021. Hyvärinen et al. (2022) present the results of the characterizing tests along with a more detailed presentation of the facility design philosophy and structure. The MOTEL test facility is a model of

Fig. 11. Nuclear material safeguards during the life cycle of the nuclear facility, connections of different actors.

an SMR with a resemblance to the design of the NuScale type SMR. The unique modularity configuration of the MOTEL facility design and construction is presented in Fig. 10. The figure shows how the main part of the facility, the pressure vessel package, is constructed of the four main modules, i.e., a core, an extension piece, a steam generator, and a pressurizer module.

Traditionally in integral test facilities, the core with the heater rods is made long and thin to preserve the height scaling of 1:1 compared with the reference core in question. With MOTEL, the practice is not followed. Instead, the core of MOTEL has been designed wider and shorter than

usual to enable studying both axial and radial flow phenomena inside the core region. The core heater rod bundle design is generic and does not directly represent the fuel design of any existing reactor type. The heater rods in the core are arranged in a rectangular grid.

An essential feature in the MOTEL design is the helical coil steam generator construction. A specific characteristic of this type of steam generator is that the secondary side flow and boiling takes place inside the steam generator tubes, whereas the primary side water flows outside the tubes, through the shell side of the steam generator tube bundles. The steam generator is comprised of altogether 16 tubes.

Fig. 12. Spreading of the radioactive cloud and gained dose from the release of 1TBq activity (Cs, Kr, I) as a function of distance and time using three different stability classes and three stack heights.

Fig. 13. LUT HEating Reactor, LUTHER, a 24 MWth LWR-based district heating reactor concept.

The behaviour of the helical coil steam generator and core cross flows were studied within the Euratom-funded McSAFER project in 2021–2022. McSAFER is a Euratom-funded project with a collaboration of 13 organizations coordinated by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology. The project aims to advance the safety research for SMRs by combining experiments and numerical simulations (Sanchez-Espinoza et al., 2021).

Two series of experiments were conducted with MOTEL within the McSAFER project. The first series studied the behaviour of the helical coil steam generator of MOTEL. Steady states with different core power levels were run, and particularly the temperature behaviour of the steam generator, both on the shell and tube sides, was studied. The unstable superheating behaviour at higher heating powers warrants further investigations to determine the operating parameter boundaries for the stable behaviour of the facility. Telkkä et al., (2023b) present the results of the steam generator experiments.

The second series focused on studying core crossflows by applying asymmetrical radial core power distributions to achieve as large temperature differences as possible in the radial direction of the core. A specific aim of the experiments was to provide measurement data for the validation of thermal-hydraulic systems, subchannel and CFD codes within the project.

3.2. Supporting legislation for SMR licensing

The PIEMOS project (Hujala et al., 2022) covers opportunities and development needs associated with new technology Small Modular serially produced nuclear reactors, SMRs. This research was ordered by the Finnish government and published in a series of the Government's analysis, assessment, and research activities in 2022. The PIEMOS research group consisted of LUT University experts with two outside experts.

The PIEMOS project considered how the Finnish nuclear energy act should be adapted to consider new small, modular, serially produced reactor technologies. The study rested on publicly available information on nuclear reactor technology, the history of nuclear regulation in Finland, experiences of nuclear licensing and oversight practices, the opportunity to produce heat and cogeneration in addition to electricity

only, and new business models enabled by small unit size.

This project considered siting, nuclear materials, and nuclear technologies, in particular the size of the emergency protection zone, underground siting, land use planning, and environmental impact assessment of projects and regulations. Regarding nuclear materials, the study covered nuclear fuel and nuclear waste management as well as nuclear safeguards. Fig. 11 presents an example of how different operators are related together during the life cycle of a nuclear facility from the perspective of nuclear safeguards. Regarding technology, the study covered the effects of modularity on applications, implementation, use of existing technologies and avoidance of expensive special products, passive safety, and impact of unit size on the licensing system.

The project concluded that the nuclear energy act should be complemented with separate approval processes for both reactor technology and plant site, to ensure the benefits of serial production. It is also possible to clarify the intent and purpose of the Government's Decision-in-Principle. Safety assessment and protection zone sizing should be performance-based.

One significant difference between traditional-size reactors and small modular reactors is SMRs' possibility for underground or partly underground siting where only the stack of the power plant is over the ground. An important question is whether an SMR needs a stack. The presence of the stack was assumed, because it is part of the ventilation, and it is always better to spread possible released activity no matter how large or small. In normal use, small activity release is possible and spreading it with the stack makes it smaller. In a potential accident situation spreading the released activity might help the clearing of the area and keep the site area accessible for the rescue personnel. In the project, one main goal was to find out suitable, safe enough exclusion area size for the SMRs. This depends on the used stack height. A Simple Gaussian pollution distribution model with Pasquill's stability classes was used in this study (Pasquill, 1961; Zannetti, 1990). Fig. 12 presents an example of the spreading of 1 TBq released radioactive dose in the first 48 h at three different stack heights: 5 m, 25 m and 100 m at three different stability classes: a bright sunny day, a cloudy day/night and a bright winter night. Research showed that new stack heights can be considered, but attention must be paid to the magnitude of actual release to keep doses acceptable.

3.3. District heating reactor development

Electricity generation in Finland has since the mid-2010 s been largely based on carbon-free sources, hydropower, nuclear and biomass-based cogeneration. Therefore, carbon dioxide emissions are typically quite small, within 50 to 100 gCO₂/kWh. However, district heating, the predominant space heating method in Finland, still relies on fossil fuels such as peat and natural gas to about 40 %.

A nuclear reactor produces heat and would therefore be an ideal power source for district heating. Nuclear reactors have been developed for heat-only supply in China and Russia, in the power range of 70 to 400 MWth, but none of the recent designs has been deployed. In the Finnish context, supply in the order of 1000 MWth is needed only in the metropolitan area of the capital Helsinki. Elsewhere in the country, heating season (approximately 9 months, September through May) demand is in the few tens to some hundred MWths, directly proportional to the size of the population supplied. For supply security reasons it is desirable to provide several units for each consumer network. The small size of the long-term baseload heat demand naturally then leads to the need for a smallish unit size.

LUT University Nuclear Engineering laboratory has been sketching a novel light-water reactor design LUTHER for district heating purposes (Truong et al., 2021). This reactor is rated at 24 MWth and envisioned for below-grade installation to protect against external threats. Passive safety has been designed in the system to simplify the safety case and minimize cost. A sketch of the reactor is provided in Fig. 13. Development of this design is currently progressing slowly due to staff shortage.

4. Gas-cooled reactor safety, safety justification of novel technologies

Future reactors, large or small, could be based on multiple different fuels, coolants and use cases. Section 4.1 presents gas-cooled reactor research carried out at LUT University. Section 4.2 applies the safety case construction approach of Section 6.3 to a gas-cooled microreactor concept, currently being considered for deployment in Lappeenranta City.

4.1. Gas-cooled reactor related studies

Internationally, R&D interest towards Generation IV nuclear energy systems (Gen IV) started to grow in the early 2000 s spearheaded by the Generation IV International Forum (GIF) (Kelly, 2014). The Gen IV research was followed and, to some extent, participated also by Finland via international collaborations and as domestically funded research projects. The most notable national research project on Gen IV technologies was the New Type Nuclear Reactors (NETNUC) funded by the Academy of Finland and Fortum between 2008 and 2011 (Kyrki-Rajamäki et al., 2009; Suikkanen, 2012). NETNUC was realized as a collaboration between LUT, Aalto University and VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland and included a wide portfolio of Gen IV-related research topics. The focus of research at LUT within 6.3 was on gas-cooled reactor technologies, especially the pebble bed type high-temperature reactor which was of interest especially due to the promising developments at the time, first in South Africa with the pebble bed modular reactor (PBMR) (Koster et al., 2003) and later on in China with the high-temperature reactor pebble bed module (HTR-PM) (Zhang et al., 2009). Gas-cooled high-temperature reactors were also considered of interest with their potential to broaden the application area of nuclear energy from electricity production to industrial processes. Gas-cooled reactor research at LUT initiated in NETNUC was later continued with further domestic funding and through participation in the Thermal Hydraulics of Innovative Nuclear Systems (THINS) project funded by the European Commission (Roelofs et al., 2012). The scope of all the gas-cooled reactor research at LUT was limited to numerical simulations and the development of calculation methods. A summary and main

outcome of the gas-cooled reactor research activities at LUT are provided in the following paragraphs.

The unique design feature in pebble bed reactors is that the fissile material is in the form of TRISO particles randomly dispersed inside graphite spheres and the spheres themselves are let to freely settle inside the core cavity under gravity resulting in an unordered geometric configuration. As a starting point in core neutronic and thermal-hydraulic models, this geometric randomness needs to be considered in one way or another. Although algorithms exist for generating dense packings of spheres considering only geometric constraints, a physics-based approach in the form of the discrete element method (DEM) was adopted at LUT to obtain representative information on the pebble bed packing structure. A DEM simulation considers the body forces, namely gravity, as well as the contact forces between pebbles and can be used to simulate the compaction process of the pebble bed. DEM is a computing-intensive method, but it was considered worthwhile as it can be further utilized for the analyses of the pebble flow and any other imaginable dynamic process that the pebble bed might experience. There was also previous experience from other application areas and an in-house DEM code at LUT that could be utilized, which was adapted for pebble bed packing simulations (Suikkanen et al., 2014a). First, the pebble bed radial packing density profiles resulting from DEM simulations were compared against experimental data to validate the in-house code for this application. Second, packing simulations were performed to figure out the effect of simulation and physical parameters, such as the pebble friction and restitution coefficients, on the density and structure of the resulting pebble bed when compacted under gravity. This was found useful, considering further neutronic and/or thermal-hydraulic analyses where one might wish to perform sensitivity analyses with higher or lower than nominal packing densities.

After the initial pebble bed packing investigations, the applicability of DEM was demonstrated also for dynamic situations including pebble flow and a control blade insertion related for the fluoride salt cooled pebble bed variant (Suikkanen et al., 2017). However, the focus was shifted more towards neutronic and thermal hydraulic simulations utilizing DEM to obtain realistic information of the geometric structure of the pebble bed. The Monte Carlo code Serpent was selected as the tool for neutronic analyses of pebble bed reactors, as in general, the Monte Carlo approach is directly applicable for practically any reactor design with arbitrary level of detail. Furthermore, the code being intensively developed in Finland at the time (Leppänen et al., 2015), close collaboration with the developers at VTT was natural and led to the implementation of new routines to Serpent for efficient handling of the two-level double heterogeneity represented by the TRISO particles in the fuel pebbles and the pebbles in the pebble bed (Rintala et al., 2015). Serpent was first applied to analyse various existing pebble bed criticality benchmarks of which the ones performed in the ASTRA critical facility in Russia were most thoroughly investigated and published. The ASTRA experiment with its rather complex geometry consisting of recesses in the boundary walls and several instrument tubes and a control rod tube inside the pebble bed was considered as an excellent example calling for a method like DEM for producing the pebble bed geometry for Serpent. At this stage, available open-source DEM codes with more versatile boundary geometry models were investigated as alternatives for the inhouse code. The DEM code ESyS-Particle was used in the initial work (Suikkanen et al., 2010) later followed by the DEM code LIGGGHTS in a more refined analysis of the ASTRA benchmark (Rintala et al., 2015). The analyses demonstrated that Serpent, complemented with a realistic pebble bed geometries obtained with DEM, can be efficiently used for neutronic analyses of pebble beds with fully resolved stochastic geometry ranging from the TRISO particles to the pebble bed, and thus reduce the uncertainties related to geometric approximations and simplifications.

Thermal hydraulic analysis capabilities for pebble bed reactors at LUT were initially developed by applying porous media approximation with literature correlations for the pebble bed porosity in an

Fig. 14. Vertical cross sections from a coupled simulation of a pebble bed reactor core (Suikkanen, 2014). From left to right: Power in pebbles obtained with a Monte Carlo neutronic simulation with the pebble bed geometry obtained from a DEM simulation, Pebble powers mapped to a thermal hydraulic calculation mesh as power densities, temperatures obtained from a thermal hydraulic simulation, temperatures from thermal hydraulic simulation results mapped as pebble surface temperatures for the next neutronic simulation.

axisymmetric geometry (Suikkanen, 2008). A CFD solution with all the pebbles explicitly resolved was considered unfeasible even in a research reactor scale with a total number of pebbles in tens of thousands rather

than hundreds of thousands as in power reactors. Although not for pebble bed reactors, detailed CFD simulations were performed at LUT for single rod geometries applicable for gas cooled fast reactors. This

	Normal operation	Anticipated Operational Occurrences	Design Basis Accidents	Limited fuel damage	“Core melt”
Criticality control / Shutdown	Coolant flow rate Control rod drop	Control rod drop	Shutdown rod drop	Core heatup	N/A, reactivity addition impossible in any event
Core heat removal	Forced circulation > Intermediate loop	Forced circulation > Intermediate loop	Heat conduction > Cavity cooling air loop	Heat conduction > Ground	Heat conduction > Ground
Ultimate heat sink	Intermediate loop > Adjacent plant	Intermediate loop > Atmosphere	Atmosphere, directly	Ground > Atmosphere	Ground > Atmosphere
Containment (Fuel)	TRISO + FCM™	TRISO + FCM™	Primary fuel design features	Diverse fuel design features	No release beyond DBA/BDBA
Confinement (Systems and Struct)	Closed helium loop	P&T transient protections	Retention in buildings Interm. loop isolation	Retention in conf vessel Interm. loop isolation	Retention in buildings Interm. loop integrity
Electric power supply	Main transmission grid	Main or aux grid (no LOOP with reactor trip)	Auxiliary grid (no LOOP with reactor trip)	Design optimization underway	Design optimization underway
Conditions management (HVAC)	Normal HVAC in buildings	Normal HVAC in buildings	Control room isolation (if onsite); I&C TBD	Control room isolation (if onsite); I&C TBD	Control room isolation (if onsite); I&C TBD

Fig. 15. An overall safety model for the MMR (provisional), based on IAEA SSR 2/1 Rev 1. Diversity of safety functions is readily apparent, as is the role of elementary physical processes of heat conduction and heat radiation for passive cooling.

work, aimed at code validation with experimental data for a smooth rod (Gomez et al., 2015) and for a rod with ribs on its surface (Suikkanen, 2014) highlighted the importance of sufficient level of turbulence modelling for obtaining reasonable heat transfer results. In pebble bed reactor studies, the interest was in full core analyses for which the porous media approach was considered most appropriate. The porous media modelling was further developed to utilize pebble packing information directly from DEM simulations instead of literature correlations. A method was developed and implemented as a Matlab tool to extract porosity and interfacial surface area data directly to a 3D thermal hydraulic calculation mesh superimposed over the pebble bed obtained from a DEM simulation (Suikkanen, 2014; Suikkanen et al., 2014b). This way, a mapping between a continuum based thermal hydraulic model and discrete models including both DEM and Monte Carlo neutronics was established for data transfer. In addition to packing structure data, the mapping could be used to exchange pebble bed power distributions solved with Serpent to temperature distributions solved with the thermal hydraulic solver, for which Ansys Fluent was used. This way coupled analysis capabilities were established between neutronics and gas flow with heat transfer with both models utilizing realistic pebble bed packing structure information (Suikkanen, 2014; Suikkanen et al., 2014b; Rintala, 2022). These capabilities were also successfully demonstrated in full power reactor scale as shown in Fig. 14.

4.2. Lappeenranta MMR (Micro Modular Reactor) safety case

In December 2022 LUT University and Ultra Safe Nuclear Corporation (USNC) agreed on a pre-feasibility study to explore building USNC's MMR™ gas-cooled graphite-moderated prismatic fuel reactor in Lappeenranta. The study considers reactor powers ranging from 15 to 30 MWth, with heat supply to the City of Lappeenranta as the main objective. In addition to direct heat supply, the high-temperature heat produced by the MMR™ could be used to produce electricity at high efficiency and to improve the efficiency of hydrogen production through high-temperature electrolysis.

The safety case of the MMR™ rests largely, but not exclusively, on the performance of Fully Ceramic Micro Encapsulated (FCM®) fuel. To pave the way for efficient regulation of non-LWR technology, rules that originated for LWRs must be replaced with rules that recognize the strengths and weaknesses inherent in the new technology.

As described in more detail in Section 6.4, the safety case can be constructed by overlaying key safety functions on the five defence levels of IAEA SSR-2/1 Rev 1 (IAEA, 2016), and identifying which processes, structures, or systems are involved in the performance of the safety function on each level. Small reactors in general and gas-cooled reactors in particular rely heavily on inherent processes to perform safety functions such as reactor shutdown and core heat removal. Fig. 15 illustrates the application of the Overall Safety model on the MMR; some design features of the reactor are still evolving as of this writing, and therefore several items in the figure may be subject to change.

This representation allows a quick yet complete oversight into what makes a reactor safe. The independence of defence lines from each other can be assessed and the role of each safety significant design feature as part of the overall safety case can be seen.

5. Use and developments of advanced measurement systems

LUT University Nuclear Engineering laboratory has devoted significant effort to the multidimensional characterisation of single- and two-phase flows. Single-phase turbulent flow problems can be solved with Particle Image Velocimetry, two-phase flow interface area structure can be resolved with Wire Mesh Sensors, high-speed photography has been used to characterize steam bubble dynamics and chugging, and optic fibre temperature profile measurements are being introduced as this writing.

All these advanced measurement techniques are valuable for the

accurate characterization of flow phenomena and the improvement of wall functions or interfacial closure laws used in computer codes.

5.1. High-speed photographing and pattern recognition

video camera systems have been used to record thermal-hydraulic experiments for decades. The need for high-speed video recordings was recognized at LUT Nuclear Engineering in 2007 (Purhonen, 2007). In the beginning, normal-speed (25 fps) cameras were used for qualitative analyses. Later, high-speed cameras came to support other measuring techniques. LUT Nuclear Engineering has three Miro M310 HS high-speed cameras. The main goal of the high-speed video camera system has been the development of the pattern recognition-based image analysis algorithm, where high-speed video data can be used for the validation of CFD codes and support the results of the other measuring techniques (Hujala, 2019). During the past 15 years, dozens of thermal-hydraulic experiments have been recorded using several different test facilities.

The first pattern recognition algorithm for the detection of condensing steam bubbles in POOLEX tests was created in 2012 (Tanskanen, 2012; Tanskanen et al., 2014). The algorithm was improved in 2013 (Hujala, 2013). The first algorithms were made for normal speed cameras. The new, currently in use, high-speed camera system created the need for a new algorithm which could estimate the volume and surface area of condensing steam bubbles better than before, collect more data, and increase knowledge of the optical measuring techniques.

Data were obtained from the direct contact condensation experiment DCC-05 of the PPOOLEX test facility and the SEF-INF2 experiment of the SEF-POOL facility. The image processing toolbox of MATLAB software was used for creating an image analysis algorithm for vertical vent blowdown pipes (Hujala et al., 2018a). The algorithm evaluates the basic properties of condensing steam bubbles, such as volume, surface area, surface velocity and acceleration in the vertical direction. The algorithm was used for the frequency analysis of the DCC-05 experiments data. (Hujala et al., 2018b). In the frequency analysis, the fast Fourier transform (FFT) was used to study the different frequencies of several bubble types. The data analysed with the algorithm could determine the critical wavelength of condensation-driven Rayleigh-Taylor instability (RTI) (Patel et al., 2017). This characterisation of the small interface deformations must also be taken into consideration when generating the grid size for a CFD simulation. Frequency analysis results were also compared to the CFD data. The algorithm developed to analyse experimental data was also applied to give input to CFD application and to compare the results of the CFD simulations to data as presented in Chapter 2.4.

The algorithm was extended to cover steam injection from a horizontal sparger orifice (Hujala et al., 2019). Here the challenge was to characterise multiple moving bubbles. Improvements were made especially for the evaluation of the surface velocities and accelerations which were calculated for all angles between 0° to 360° of projected 2D plane instead of vertical direction. This successfully improved the algorithm such that it can track multiple bubbles and process their respective data. All cases were bound together from the point of view of CFD validation in 2023 (Patel et al., 2023).

5.2. Optic fibres

In experimental nuclear thermal hydraulic research, optic fibres for temperature measurement have been applied in several studies, such as those conducted by Lomperski et al. (2017). Optic fibers have been used in LUT Nuclear Engineering Lab since 2018. The system is commercially available from Luna Inc. The system is so-called High-Definition Distributed Fibre Optic Sensing (HD-FOS) which offers sub-millimetre spatial resolution for both temperature and strain with measurement frequencies up to 80 Hz. The adaptation of optic fibres has been active during recent years at LUT Nuclear Engineering Lab. The capability to

Fig. 16. The histograms of temperature deviations for SC fibre (left) and reference thermocouples, TCs, (right) from different temperature ranges.

measure 1D temperature profiles from complex geometries can offer novel information for both system thermal hydraulics and CFD. The final goal when applying optic fibres is to achieve capability to use optic fibres as a stand-alone temperature measurement.

At LUT both HD optic fibres and newly available strain-compensated (SC) fibres have been utilized. The HD optic fibres offer maximum spatial resolution of 0.65 mm with temporal resolution of 20 Hz (and higher temporal resolution when the spatial resolution is lowered). The SC fibres offer spatial resolution of 10.4 mm with 2.5 Hz frequency. The lower spatiality of the SC fibre is said to be compensated with more accurate results which has been tested in extensive experiment series with IDEAL (SAFIR2022) and DEMAIN (SAFER2028) projects. Minimizing mechanical stress induced by the installation is paramount for the application of the sensors. Any strain imposed to the fibre which is not due to thermal expansion is sensed, being the biggest error source for the optic fibre measurement. The SC fibre is said to overcome this but testing which is done against thermocouples is not showing promising results yet for the SC fibre. The testing of the optic fibres will continue throughout 2023 within DEMAIN project. A typical deviation from similar vertical temperature profiles for SC and HD fibres are presented in Fig. 16.

The optic fibres can also be used for 2D temperature and strain field measurement and to some extent for 3D volume measurement, yet only 1D temperature distributions are utilized so far. In addition to 1D temperature profile measurements with optic fibres, LUT Nuclear Engineering Lab is developing and experimenting with the strain sensor for pipe 1D pressure profile measurement outside the pipe. When it succeeds it will offer novel information for critical flow studies conducted within C-FLOW project.

5.3. Particle image velocimetry

Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) has widely been applied in the LUT Nuclear Engineering Lab. PIV is an optical velocity measurement technique that utilizes laser-illuminated seeding particles as tracers of the flow. The particle images are captured with imaging optics and analysed finally as 2D velocity plane. Depending on the PIV setup, the 2D velocity plane can be either two-component (2C: x,y) or three-component (3C: x,

Fig. 17. The mock-up (left) and the planar-PIV setup with optical access to the mock-up for velocity measurement (right).

y,z) vector field. 2D2C vector fields are measured with planar-PIV setup utilizing double-pulsed Nd:YAG laser as a light source and one camera perpendicular to the measurement plane. 2D3C vector fields are measured with stereo-PIV setup utilizing two cameras in an angle towards the measurement plane (Raffel et al., 2007).

LUT Nuclear Engineering Lab uses LaVision's PIV system. The laser used to create the needed laser sheet for illuminating the tracer particles in the measurement plane is double-cavity Nd:YAG laser with 180 mJ pulse maximum power and 15 Hz repetition rate. The pulse wavelength is 532 nm. For imaging, two LaVision sCMOS cameras are used with 5

Fig. 18. Vector velocity field of natural convection scheme in an enclosure with left wall heated.

MPixel sensor and 50 Hz imaging frequency. The sensor pixel size is $6.5 \times 6.5 \mu\text{m}^2$. The system is the so-called slow speed system capable of 15 Hz measuring frequency as it is capped by the light source's frequency. LUT Nuclear Laboratory has plans to update the PIV system to high-speed PIV by means of higher repetition rate laser light source and high-speed cameras. The PIV system is operatable in two-phase or with non-condensable gas by means of phase-separation utilizing Rhodamin-B doped PMMA particles as tracers. In addition, filters are installed on camera lenses to separate 532 nm laser light reflections from bubbles from the larger wavelength light emitted from particles.

The system has been used both in academic and contract research for industrial partners. The system has been applied for measuring velocity fields of an industrial-size oil burner and on many occasions in one-phase water flows which PIV has proved to be a powerful tool. One of the successfully conducted studies had the objective of defining the heat transfer characteristics related to pressurized thermal shock (PTS) in cold leg ECC injection discussed earlier in Section 2.5. The mock-up had a heated steel block as a reactor pressure vessel (RPV) wall model with multiple thermocouples attached to the surface. The mock-up had

windows installed to have optical access for the camera and laser sheet for PIV. The mock-up with the accompanied PIV setup is presented in Fig. 17.

PIV was mainly utilized to validate pre-test 2D CFD analyses. Several tests were executed with changing parameters of forced convection and natural convection schemes. In addition, a rectangular obstacle was attached to the heated wall and the experiments were run with changing water temperature and flow rate. In addition, the obstacle was taken out to get comparative data from normal flow in the channel without the obstacle. The obstacle size was varied (100 %, 50 %, 37.5 %, 25 %, and 12.5%) and respective velocity fields were measured.

PIV proved to be a very powerful tool as in the pre-test phase it revealed velocity fields that differed drastically from the pre-test simulations done with CFD. The ultimate reason for this was a misplaced flange connection in the inlet of the mock-up. With the help of PIV, the problem was identified, and the rest of the measurement campaign was successfully conducted. Altogether 138,000 particle image pairs were recorded during the measurement campaigns. An example vector velocity field of natural convection scheme, when the mock-up wall was

Fig. 19. Time-averaged void fraction distributions with different pipe inclinations measured with the AXE sensor, superficial velocities: $J_L = 1,2$ m/s and $J_G = 0,6$ m/s.

heated, is presented in Fig. 18. The latest, PIV was used to validate ultrasonic velocity meters which are used in MOTEL facility's annular downcomer (Saira, 2021).

5.4. Wire-Mesh sensors

The wire-mesh sensor (WMS) measurement technique was originally developed by Prasser et al. (1998) for measuring and visualizing multiphase flows, when the phases have a significant difference in conductivity. Various WMS designs have been developed and applied for single- and two-phase flow studies over recent years. The design and the construction of the sensor can vary depending on the purpose of the research. Most typically, the WMSs installed in pipelines have been installed across the flow. These cross-sectional, i.e., radial, sensors are used to obtain instantaneous or averaged cross-sectional distributions of the flow area. This traditional approach is not ideal if the scope of the study is to measure the development or the dynamics of the flow in the axial direction. Hence, the axially aligned conductivity wire-mesh sensor (named AXE) has been designed and tested at the LUT nuclear safety research laboratory. The sensor has 16 x 128 wires placed with the 3 mm x 3 mm spatial resolution over the area of 45 x 381 mm².

In the future, implementing axial wire-mesh sensors to certain test facility configurations could significantly improve the CFD code validation capabilities as well as increase the understanding of two-phase flow phenomena in important nuclear safety research applications. An axial sensor is needed for e.g., applications where gradual evolution of the phase interface is of interest, such as direct contact condensation (DCC). The shape and dynamics of the interface affect interfacial transfer processes. However, before moving into thermal non-equilibrium situations, testing in adiabatic conditions is needed for a deeper understanding of how much the sensor disturbs the flow.

Conducted studies with the AXE sensor at LUT includes void fraction measuring and velocity field estimation of two-phase flow (Ylönen and Hyvärinen, 2015, Telkkä et al., 2018). The measurements were conducted in the adiabatic test loop with various pipeline inclinations between vertical and horizontal positions. Along with the axial sensor, measurements with a traditional cross-sectional sensor (32 x 32 sensor) were performed to study the intrusiveness of the axial sensor. It was

concluded that the void fraction distributions were qualitatively very similar for both axial and radial sensors, and that the AXE sensor did not cause irrecoverable redistribution of the flow in the performed tests. An example of time-averaged void fraction distributions with different pipeline inclinations measured with the axial sensor is presented in Fig. 19.

Concerning the velocity fields estimated from the data, the study revealed that the AXE sensor disturbs the two-phase flow by slowing it down as the velocities were consistently lower than those measured with the cross-sectional WMS.

The studies with the AXE sensor continued with void fraction measurements in swirling two-phase flow. Swirling flows, and in particular phase separation in swirling flow, are of interest in steam separator performance assessment. For this purpose, two swirl generators with different blade angles were manufactured: 60° and 30°, the latter causing a stronger swirling effect to the flow. The swirl generators were designed to resemble the one tested by Kataoka et al. (2009).

The results from the axial sensor measurements with both 30° and 60° swirl generators together with the comparative measurements with the cross-sectional WMS revealed that the axial sensor is not able to produce reliable void fraction data from swirling two-phase flow. The axial sensor produces void fraction values, which are significantly lower than those measured with the cross-sectional sensor. Also, the shapes of the void fraction profiles differ from the traditional sensor data. The axial sensor produces much more asymmetric void fraction distributions compared with the cross-sectional sensor. This results from the intrusive character of the AXE sensor, especially its leading edge, which significantly disturbs the swirling flow. (Telkkä et al., 2019a).

6. Outlook on future developments

In the near term, system thermal hydraulic research continues on topics found challenging to reactor safety and/or computer modelling. Section 6.1 discusses continuation of experiments on detrimental effect of non-condensable gases inside the primary system, already mentioned in Section 2.3. Section 6.2 describes a return to roots of system thermal hydraulics and revisit of two-phase critical flow, especially for very long tubes ($L/D > 100$). Section 6.3 describes hardware updates

Fig. 20. The facility used for critical flow discharges as of May 2023 (the design may still evolve). The discharge is collected inside the containment model PPOOLEX.

foreseen at LUT and Section 6.4 development of a transparent overall safety justification approach.

6.1. Phenomena of near-term interest: Non-condensable gas interference on primary depressurisation, performance of open natural circulation loops, helical coil steam generators

As discussed in Section 2.3, the effect of nitrogen on core cooling during a SBLOCA has been studied experimentally with the PWR PACTEL facility of LUT University (Riikonen et al., 2018). It was observed that after having a SBLOCA in the hot leg, nitrogen released from an accumulator can prevent primary side depressurization and cause a core heat-up at the reactor pressure above or very close to a typical low-pressure safety injection shut-off head. It was found to be important to have more testing to map the range of the pressures at which the observed decoupling of the primary and secondary side pressures appears as a function of the break size, released nitrogen mass, and primary side volume available for nitrogen. In the Finnish Research Program on Nuclear Power Plant Safety 2019–2022 (SAFIR2022), the first experiments of this series related to the released nitrogen mass, and primary side volume available for nitrogen were carried out. The effect of the break size on the nitrogen release and the decoupling of the pressures is planned to be studied in 2024 or 2025.

The open loop heat transfer performance experiments with the PASI test facility continue in the EU PASTELS project with funding from the European Commission Horizon 2020 program, as described in Section 2.2. Outside of the PASTELS scope, there are still open issues to be studied concerning the open loop functioning. For example, the conditions where the loop flow stabilises (oscillations fade out) are planned to be studied in the SAFER2028 GRAF project (to be reported in due

course).

If new reactor types are being developed commercially, questions related to them may arise, and finding answers to these questions most likely will require both integral facilities and setups devoted to specific phenomena. Many new steam generator configurations have been designed to superheat the live steam, and this must be demonstrated. Likewise, flow stability is an important feature of helical coil steam generators. Thermal oscillation might challenge the tube integrity and thereby the reliable operation of such steam generators (Reyes, 2022; Zhang, 2022). The Modular Test Loop MOTEL, described in Section 3.1, is being employed in the EU McSAFER project funded by the European Commission Horizon 2020 program (Sanchez-Espinoza et al., 2021) to characterize the helical coil steam generator performance and flow distribution in a nonuniformly heated reactor core. In these experiments, some issues related to the helical coil steam generator flow stability have been observed. The unstable and oscillating flow conditions can reduce the structural strength of the system and shorten its lifetime. With the MOTEL experiments planned to be carried out in the GRAF project, the range of stable operating conditions can be defined.

6.2. Phenomena of near-term interest: Two-phase critical flow

Interest in the two-phase critical flow (TPCF) model development has arisen both internationally and nationally, after decades of dormancy. The state-of-the-art of thermal-hydraulic system code prediction of TPCF was updated in 2020 within FONESYS network (Ahn et al., 2015). In the benchmark, eight system codes (CATHARE2, RELAP5/MOD3.3, TRACE v5.0, ATHLET, SPACE, MARS, COSINE, and APROS) were utilised in prediction of six experiments, both in transient and steady-state (Super CANON: Sekri, 1982; Edwards Pipe: Edwards &

O'Brien, 1979; UCL Experiment: Attou et al., 2000; Super Moby-Dick: Riegel, 1978; Sozzi-Sutherland: Sozzi&Sutherland, 1975; and Brookhaven National Laboratory: Abuaf et al., 1981). The analyses revealed that there is still a sizable prediction error of TPCF depending on the subcooling level of the stagnation condition. The maximum absolute relative error can be up to $\sim 40\%$ in near-saturation upstream condition, and even in high subcooling up to $\sim 20\%$ (Lanfardini et al., 2020). The work for developing TPCF modelling is ongoing within SILENCE network (Aksan et al., 2018; Silence, 2023) where LUT is a participating member. During 2021–2022, the SILENCE members discussed how to implement different measurement methods for TPCF, and which are still the biggest uncertainties for TPCF model development. The results of the discussions will be published at the NURETH-20 conference in 2023 (Bestion et al., 2023).

In addition to international efforts for TPCF model development, national interest has arisen for studies on critical flow, mainly to verify code performance for steam generator tube rupture analyses that involve critical flow at the end of very long tubes. The national studies started in the CRITFLO project within SAFIR2022 with providing a literary survey on the experimental work on critical flow studies. The ongoing C-FLOW project within SAFER2028 will design, build, and commission a specific effects test facility (SET), capable of TPCF discharges. During 2023, LUT will construct a new test facility that is capable of critical flow discharges and can be used for TPCF model development. The facility will consist of an upstream pressure vessel, a section with instrumentation for measuring the critical mass flow, and smaller diameter discharge tubes with representative sizes of PWRs used in Finland ($\sim\varnothing 13\text{--}17\text{ mm}$). The maximum achievable upstream pressure will be 10 MPa and maximum temperature 270 °C (subcooling of $\sim 41\text{ °C}$ at maximum pressure). The facility model is presented in Fig. 20.

During 2023, the experiment work will begin with proof-of-concept tests and the experiment program will be expanded in 2024–2025. The ultimate goal is to use transparent discharge tubes accompanied with high-speed imaging and pattern-recognition algorithm to get information on details of flashing occurring in the discharge pipes. The facility will be equipped with traditional temperature and pressure measurements alongside 1D scanning of the density in the discharge tube with gamma densitometer. In addition, the full 1D pressure profile of the discharge tube will be measured with optical strain fibre alongside normal discrete point pressure measurements with pressure gauges. The temperature of the discharge tube outside can be used to estimate the average temperature of the water-steam mixture discharging. The 1D temperature profile of the tube will be measured with optic fibre alongside ultrasonic temperature gauges. The ultrasonic temperature gauges will be installed in discrete points along the tube, and one is installed to the same housing with the gamma densitometer to obtain both the density and the tube temperature at the same time at the same point.

Within the C-FLOW project, new experts will be educated in the means of conducting Master Theses on different topics in relation to TPCF. The reflections and knowledge sharing between experimentalists and code developers/users will be conducted between C-FLOW and the THEME project of VTT. The need for closer cooperation between experimenters and analysts was voiced also in the FONESYS benchmark. Eventually, TPCF model development will be carried out by LUT in cooperation with VTT, and SILENCE members. Novel instrumentation will be built within the DEMAİN project of LUT within the SAFER2028 National Research Program. There is also a plan to update the upstream pressure vessel in the future within the DEMAİN project for achieving the EPR primary pressure level of 15.5 MPa. In the beginning stages, the discharge will be into atmospheric pressure, and the PPOOLEX facility at LUT will be used as the downstream discharge vessel. During SAFER2028, the new facility will undergo structural changes depending on the resources available in the future. Initially, the critical flow discharges will be of transient nature (as is the PRISE itself) but steady-state discharges by using a back-pressure downstream vessel are planned.

6.3. Development of research infrastructure

LUT University's thermal hydraulic research laboratory has evolved over the decades according to the national and international research needs in the field. In the early years in the 1970 s and 1980 s, the interest was particularly on various loss-of-coolant accident phenomena. Studied phenomena included e.g., reflooding heat transfer, natural circulation heat transfer, gravitational cooling, and boron crystallization. In the 1970 s, especially the large break LOCA scenarios were studied. After the Three Mile Island accident in 1979, the focus shifted on the small break LOCAs, which affected the development of test facilities and created a need to modify existing or build integral facilities including the whole primary circuit of a PWR. Thus, the PACTEL facility, which models a primary circuit of a VVER-440, was designed and built in the LUT laboratory in 1990. PACTEL was updated in 2009 with the application of two new circuits and two vertical steam generators modelling the EPR type steam generators.

In addition to the studies with integral test facilities, various phenomena studies have been conducted with separate effects test facilities in the LUT laboratory according to current needs. These include for example containment studies performed with the PPOOLEX facility, various insulation debris material studies, and studies related to passive safety.

The LUT laboratory has also reacted to the emerging interest in SMRs in recent years. The MOTEL test facility, which represents a prototypical SMR operating with natural circulation, was commissioned in 2020, as described in the earlier Chapters. The facility enables experimental research of thermal hydraulic features related to SMRs.

In a thermal hydraulic research laboratory that includes large-scale and small-scale test facilities, maintaining and developing the research infrastructure is vital. The LUT laboratory has a dedicated project for the maintenance and development of the infrastructure under the Finnish national research program. The project enables the ongoing maintenance and development of the research infrastructure. In addition to the hardware upkeep, the maintenance of expertise, as well as the training of young experts, is also an essential part of the project. (Telkkä et al., 2019b, Telkkä et al., 2023c).

Ongoing, high-quality maintenance work is essential in keeping the existing test facilities operable and thus secure their availability for research projects and possible fast-arising research needs from the power plants. Maintenance includes repairation works of the facilities when needed. The LUT laboratory has in-house facility designing and construction capabilities, which supports the capability of rapid response to the possible fast-emerging needs from the power plants. An important part of the infrastructure maintenance is maintaining the measurement instruments, meaning in practice the yearly calibrations of the important measurement devices such as pressure and differential pressure transducers and thermocouples for temperature measuring. The measurement devices can also be renewed when needed.

The measurement infrastructure has also been upgraded with modern, 2D/3D capable measurement systems to enhance the understanding of thermal hydraulic phenomena and to produce better data for the validation of CFD codes. These advanced measuring techniques include particle image velocimetry, wire-mesh sensors, high-speed imaging, and optical fibres. Developments and research activities related to these techniques are described in more detail in Chapter 5. LUT will upgrade the measurement capabilities soon with the procurement of a gamma tomography densitometry system.

6.4. Evolution of regulatory approach (construction of a safety case)

LUT University nuclear engineering laboratory has developed a proposal for a defence-in-depth model based on the defence-in-depth definition of IAEA Safety Fundamentals 1. This basic approach was originally developed as part of an Overall Safety study in (Hyvärinen et al., 2016; Hyvärinen et al., 2022). The approach has been

	Operational States		Accident Conditions		
	Normal Operation	Anticipated Operational Occurrences	Design Basis Accidents	Design Extension Conditions	
				Without significant fuel damage	With core melting
Subcriticality	CVCS	CVCS			"N/A"
	RCCA	RCCA	RCCA		
	Soluble boron				
	Gadolinia				
			MHSI		
Heat removal			EBS	EBS	
	SG → Condenser → CWS → Atmosphere	SG → Condenser → CWS → Atmosphere			
	RHRS		LHSI →	MHSI →	CMSS
		SG → MSSS → Atmosphere	MSSS + MHSI →	MSSS + LHSI →	
	CCWS → ESWS → UHS	CCWS → ESWS → UHS	→ CCWS → ESWS → UHS	→ CCWS → ESWS → UHS	
	MFWS	EFWS	EFWS		
Containment			IRWST	IRWST	IRWST
	Closed piping (RCPB)	Closed piping (RCPB)	RPV	RPV	
	PSRVs → PRT	PSRVs → PRT	PDS → PRT	PDS → PRT	PDS → PRT
			CIS		
			RCB	RCB	RCB
			CGCS	CGCS	CGCS
					CMSS
				SAHRS → CCWS → ESWS → UHS	
Power supply	NPSS	NPSS	EPSS (offsite/EDGs)	SBODG	SBODG
	EUPS	EUPS			
HVAC				12UPS	12UPS
	CRACS	CRACS	CRACS	CRACS	
	SBVS	SBVS	SBVS	SBVS	
	SBVSE	SBVSE	SBVSE	SBVSE	
	ESWPBVS	ESWPBVS	ESWPBVS		
	CBVS	CBVS	CBVS		
	EPGBWS	EPGBWS	EPGBWS		
SBORVS	SBORVS	SBORVS	SBORVS	SBORVS	

Fig. 21. U.S.EPR operational and safety systems presented in the Overall Safety framework. Note that there are nominally five separate defence lines, but the same systems get often credited on several lines, such that true independence exists between two or at best three lines of defence.

subsequently used to compare safety justifications on large LWRs and SMRs (Turunen, 2020) and extended to cover interactions of nuclear safety, nuclear security and nuclear safeguards (Valkeapää, 2021).

In the LUT model, the safety case can be constructed by overlaying key safety functions on the five defence levels of IAEA SSR-2/1 Rev 1, and identifying which processes, structures, or systems are involved in the performance of the safety function on each level.

As an example, Turunen (2020) analysed the safety systems of the U.S.EPR large reactor as shown in Fig. 21. The same approach can be used for SMRs and non-LWRs, as shown in Section 4.2 for the Lappeenranta MMR™ plans.

7. Conclusions

A very broad body of nuclear thermal-hydraulics experimental insight and data has been collected over the decades in LUT University, Nuclear Engineering laboratory. It has been proven time and again that experiments yield the most representative picture of how thermal-hydraulic systems and processes really function, and what they are sensitive to. Significant computational modelling capability for coupling of thermal hydraulics with reactor physics and fuel thermomechanics has also been developed. In addition to experiments and computational modelling, logical modelling of nuclear reactor safety justification on the basis of the IAEA SSR-2/1 Rev 1 definition of Defence-in-Depth has been carried out to ensure that nuclear safety can be transparently presented and assessed.

The most interesting insights and achievements so far are the following:

- 1) Immiscible fluids of equal densities can be separated from each other by flotation of one of the fluids. Judicious use of this phenomenon is the basis of the bitumen trap, that in turn allows the use of viscodampers to prevent the Olkiluoto 3 surge line vibrations.
- 2) In PWRs, nitrogen from hydroaccumulators can defeat primary depressurisation through secondary cooldown, in contrast to system code predictions using APROS and TRACE.
- 3) Minor axial offset in experimental facility construction can cause a major difference in lateral velocity profiles. CFD analysis based on ideal geometry would not detect velocity profile skewness due to geometry imperfections.
- 4) Open loop natural circulation heat removal with a containment wall cooler is not at all sensitive to the flow resistance in the downcomer loop, as long as countercurrent flow in the riser supplies the heat exchanger.
- 5) Advanced measurement methods have yielded unique insights: PIV into the details of the downcomer wall heat transfer due to turbulent single-phase flows, high-speed photography with image processing into the dynamics of direct contact condensation, wire-mesh sensors into two-phase flow interfacial area behaviour, and optic fibres into detailed axial temperature profiles.
- 6) SMR licensing specific studies for the authorities have for their part motivated the recently started revision of the Finnish nuclear energy act, to enable a wide geographic deployment of SMRs near the population centres.
- 7) Research into gas-cooled reactors has developed advanced coupled gas flow and heat transfer / reactor physical analysis methods and paved the way to the deployment of emerging technology in Lappeenranta. The MMR™ reactor will supply district heating to the city of Lappeenranta. It will also form a platform for energy system integration research, because the high-temperature heat could also be used for electricity generation and hydrogen generation.
- 8) Overall safety of any reactor design can be presented and analysed in a very compact and transparent form using the LUT model (as provided in section 6.4) overlays the safety functions on the defence lines and identifies the processes, structures and systems responsible for each function.

Based on LUT University's experience, it seems that water-cooled large nuclear reactors will survive several decades into this century, in the baseload electricity generation for large grids. Water cooled SMRs might gradually replace the large reactors, if their promises regarding rapid deployment and competitive pricing can be fulfilled.

Non-LWR SMRs and microreactors clearly have a bright future in industrial and municipal applications, if their promise regarding easy siting near the population centres can be fulfilled, in addition to economy and rapid deployment.

In order to support any kind of nuclear future, nuclear infrastructure must evolve. New technologies require new fuel supply, waste management, legal and financial frameworks, and competence by regulators for new designs. The research community, industry and regulators need to work closely together to ensure that an adequately robust infrastructure is available in time for the actual processing of the future projects, large and small, for all relevant technologies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Juhani Hyvärinen: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Vesa Riikonen:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Joonas Telkkä:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Elina Hujala:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Virpi Kouhia:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Markku Puustinen:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Giteshkumar Patel:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Lauri Pyy:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Juhani Vihavainen:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Heikki Suikkanen:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Ville Rintala:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data is available on request, when the respective financing rules permit sharing.

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